

SECTION OF BIOLOGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES

ПОЛЕНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ АЛЫЧИ РАСТОПЫРЕННОЙ (*PRUNUS DIVARICATA* L.) В УСЛОВИЯХ АПШЕРОНА

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THE PALYNOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION OF WILD PLUM (*PRUNUS DIVARICATA* L.) SPECIES IN ABSHERON CONDITION

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Аннотация

В статье изучены морфология и жизнеспособность пыльцы вида алычи растопыренной (*Prunus divaricata* Ledeb.). Проведенные поленологические исследования на пыльцевых зернах алычи растопыренной в условиях Апшерона показали, что цветочные почки из апикальной меристемы формируются на 219 день вегетационного периода. С этой целью, изучали морфологию и жизнеспособность пыльцы вида алычи растопыренной. Опыты показали, что ацетокармин окрашивает цитоплазму нормальных пыльцевых зерен в розовый цвет, ядро в бледно-красный, а стерильные пыльцевые зерна не окрашиваются и остаются желтыми. Пыльцевые зерна алычи растопыренной бледно-желтые, трех-бороздчатые, пористые, форма сплюснутая. Длина полярной оси составляет 34 мкм., экваториального диаметра 30 мкм., от полярного контура округло-треугольные, от экватора эллиптические. Оптимальная концентрация сахарозы, стимулирующая прорастание пыльцы, составила 20, при этом на следующий день после посева 75%. Выявлено, что высокая жизнеспособность пыльцы алычи растопыренной, в 20% растворе сахарозы, дает возможность использования этого вида в озеленении на Апшероне.

Abstract

The article deals with morphology and the vitality of pollens of wild plum (*Prunus divaricata* Ledeb.) species. There were carried out palynological investigations on wild plum pollen grains in Absheron conditions. So, the completely of flower buds from apical meristem expires for 219 day in vegetation period. For that end in view we first have made an attempt of studying morphology and vitality of pollen of the species *Prunus divaricata* L. The percentage of pollen grains colored by acetocarmine from total quantity gives an idea of a degree of vitality (quality) of pollen. Of course, not all morphologically valuable pollen grains colored by acetocarmine will be physiologically active when marking them on a stigma of that or other species. Acetocarmine color cytoplasm of normal pollen grains into rosy color, and the kernel of generative cell-into pale-red, but sterile pollen grains are not colored and remain yellow. The experiences have shown that the pollen grains of wild plum are pale-yellow, three-grooving and porous the form is oblate. The length of polar axis is 34 μ equatorial dm. 30 μ from the polar outline the pollen grains are rounded-triangular and from the equator are elliptic. Optimal concentration of sucrose stimulating sprouting the pollen were 20 in which next day following the sowing 75%. It was revealed that the high vitality of pollens of wild plum in 20% sucrose solution gives perspective to use this species in planting greenery and selection in Absheron.

Ключевые слова: поленологические, алыча, пыльцевые зерна, морфологические, микроскоп Humo Scope AM 7023, камера Dino-Eye, жизнеспособность, фертильность.

Keywords: palynological, wild plum, pollen grains, morphology, Humo Scope microscope AM 7023 Dino-Eye camera, vitality, fertility.

Introduction

The most actual problems of modern period to expand species content by using introduce. Study of regularities of stricture of pollen grains and their vitality is of interest for knowledge of biology of flowering and pollination of the plants, as well as their introduction systematization and selection. *Prunus divaricata* Ledeb. and other species were studied in various aspects of world literature Lisek investigated growth and yield of plum trees in response to in-row orchard floor management Khadiv *et al.*, were learned phenotypic and pomological variability among 73 accessions of *Prunus divaricata* elected from eight natural habitats

from Guilan province in the northern parts of Iran. The researchers were learned dphylo genetics of Eurasian plums, *Prunus* L. Section *Prunus Rosaceae* Juss., according to coding and non-coding chloroplast DNA sequences. In the literature have been studied the pollen species of *Rosaceae* Juss. [2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 15, 16]. The study of pollens is one of the essential factors for the flowering biology, introduction and pollination. That is the study and the determination of the features of the pollens morphology belonging to the introduce represent scientific and the practical significance.

According to the literature, there are 30 species of *Prunus* Mill. In the *Rosaceae* family, 3 types of wildlife

in Azerbaijan, 1 subspecies and 4 in culture. Species of the *Prunus* Mill., genus is tall, large, umbrella shaped trees and arms that shed their leaves in the winter. His bark is brown; his branches are spiky or thorny. Flower petals are 5, many males are plentiful, their eggs are one nest and the fruit is large. *Prunus* Mill. In the northeastern regions of the Greater Caucasus, it has spread to the middle mountain range from the Samur-Devechi plain to the 800m high forest and bushes [1].

For this purpose we have made the first attempt to study the morphology and the vitality of the pollens of wild plum *Prunus divaricata* Ledeb. Phenological observations showed that the flower buds production of wild plum occurring per year in Absheron conditions. So the complete formation of leaf and flower buds from apical meristem expires for 211-219 days in vegetation period.

In the article have been studied the seasonal growth characteristics, compatible period of seed planting; sprouts generation; morphological structure sprouts growth and development of wild plum in Absheron conditions (To the Central Botanical Garden was introduced only one species wild plum [9-12].

Purpose of the study

Currently, studies on the morphology of pollen from various crops and determining the viability of closely related species have become increasingly relevant. The analyzed the morphological structure and viability of pollen from the following specie: *Prunus divaricata* L.

Material and methods

The palynological observations were carried out in accordance to the methodology developed in primary Botanical Garden of Russia during the per vegetation period in the following phases: the beginning of buds swelling, the beginning of leafing after every 2-3 days, but in spring and in high season after days [3,4].

The morphology and the vital ability of pollens were studied by [13] method. Vitality of pollen was determined by way of sprouting on artificial medium by method of [14]. Prepared samples were investigated in Humo Scope microscope and the pictures were taken by the AM7023 Dino-Eye camera.

The object of our research is wild plum distributed in different regions of Azerbaijan. The tests were conducted on the plants introduced to Absheron peninsula in the Central Botanic garden of ANAS of Azerbaijan.

Figure 1. The bloom period of wild plum of

The percentage of pollen grains colored by acetocarmine from total quantity gives an idea of a degree of vitality (quality) of pollen. Of course, not all morphologically valuable pollen grains colored by acetocarmine will be physiologically active when marking them on a stigma of that or other species. Acetocarmine color cytoplasm of normal pollen grains into rosy color, and the kernel of a generative cell into pale-red, but sterile pollen grains are not colored and remain yellow. The experiences have shown that the pollen grains of wild plum are pale-yellow, three-grooving, porous and the form is oblate. The length of polar axis is 34 μ , equatorial diameter 30 μ from the polar outline the pollen grains are rounded-triangular and from the equator are elliptic.

Results and discussion

We found out that vitality of pollens of this species have conducted sprouting of newly gathered pollen in a humid chamber, in a hanging drop of solution of sucrose of 10-15 and 20% concentration in three reiterations (Fig. 1, 2, 3).

Sowings in distilled water served for control. Calculation of the sprouted pollen grains expressed was made next day following sowing in five eye sights. The criterion of vitality was a quantity of sprouted pollen grains expressed in the presents from total quantity of calculated pollens. Sprouting pollen of this species begins since increase of volume of pollen grains as a result of its contiguity with nutrient medium and swelling of protoplasm. Despite a presence of three sprouting fissure in pollen, only a pollen tube with thickened capsule at the end appears. We took photos of the pollens grains from microscope. According to the obtained photos we revealed that species is ellipsoidal-oval in shape.

Our studies have shown that vitality of pollen is extremely high and grows well in 20-25 percent concentrations. But in all concentrations time and percent are not the same. Optimal concentration of sucrose stimulating sprouting of the pollens were 20 in which next day following 75% pollen grains grew. On keeping pollen of wild plum in paper bags and the under of temperature 2-5°C, their vitality were maintains nearly one month (30 days). In mass bloom period of wild plum species the pollens differ with the quality and provide the fruit formation in 75 % per cent.

Figure 2. The morphology structure pollens of wild plum [10x40]

Figure 3. The sprouting of pollens in 20% sucrose solution [10x10]

The production of pollens begins in 3rd year of ontogenesis in specimen of wild plum of vegetative origin; but in seed generations it begins in 5th year. The duration of differentiation of generative buds was on average of 219 days, but for vegetative buds, this period was 211 days in Absheron conditions. It causes high percent of fructification. As a result, the seasonal growth of wild plum goes normal in Absheron conditions. By being sustainable against climatic factors makes it useful as a decorative and fruit plant introduction in Absheron.

Was investigated the morphology structure and the vitality of pollens of wild plum species in Absheron condition. Proceeding from the above-mentioned one can concluded that investigated species introduced in Absheron peninsula have higher vitality of pollen what is confirmed as well by percent of fruit setting. Was determined that the 20% sucrose solution is optimal to the sprouting of wild plum species pollens and this provides the perspective introduction. The wild plum is plant which differs by its high fertility, drought sustainability, decorative, compatibility to the soil conditions and therapy-food features.

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